

Crafts Guilds in Medieval Telangana- As Gleaned from Kannada Inscriptions from Telangana

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ABSTRACT

An attempt is made in the present paper to make a brief survey of the trade, and Crafts guilds, of the region through ages in general and that of the period in particular to understand in proper perspective, the corporate activities of the guilds. Since antiquity, the people of Telangana region showed a keen interest in trade and commerce. The dangers on the high ways inspired the traders to travel in groups under the leadership of a Sarthavaha. Economic development of the region, during medieval period, depended upon many factors such as; 1. Geography, 2. Political conditions, 3. Social institutions and customs, 4. Transport and communication. Despite disturbed political conditions and frequent changes of ruling families, trade and commerce in this region seems to have flourished without much interruption. The valuable gifts made by the traders, merchants and their wives were possible because of the wealth and prosperity of the trading community. The inscriptions from various sites from different parts of Telangana record the donations made by a class of people called Sresthins' or Settis' appearing to be respectable tradesmen enjoying special position of honour among the members of their profession.

Key Words: guilds, shrenis, crafts, trade.telika, Panneamvaru, Kampulu and salevaru

1. Introductions

Kakatiyas brought the entire Andhradesha under their rule. The reigns of Ganapati Deva and his daughter, Rudrama Devi, form the most glorious period of the Kakatiya history. It was under Ganapati Deva, the Kakatiyas sway attained its widest expansion and their armies carried the limits of the empire, as far South as Kanchipuram and beyond.¹ The corporate activity in India can be traced back to Vedic Period, which began first in economic field. It was necessitated because of the desire to possess wealth. The acquisition of wealth was intensified by the insecurity of the times and the necessity for constant movement on the part of the traders

across the country. They required often passing through inhospitable regions and along insecure routes. Organized bands of robbers who infested these routes could be dealt successfully only by organized efforts on the part of the traders. Incidentally, this resulted to give a military dimension to the corporate activity of trading communities². Sreni is the term generally used to denote the corporation of tradesmen. This is defined as a corporation of people, following the same trade and industry irrespective of their caste. This organization corresponds to that of guilds³.

The guilds consisted of mostly workers in wood, metal, leather, stone ivory, hydraulic works and basket makers, dyers, painters, corn-dealers, cultivators, fisher folk, butchers' barbers and shampooers, garland makers and flower sellers, mariners, herdsman, robbers and free booters, forest police who guarded the caravans, money lenders, rope and matchmakers, toddy drawers, tailors and flour makers etc. Although the actual number of guilds exceeds even this number, the ideas of conventional eighteen guilds seem to have persisted down to the modern times in India⁴.

The guilds may be broadly classified into two types of viz., Trade or Merchant Guilds and Crafts or Professional Guilds. There is a clear difference in the organization of traders or merchant guilds on one side and the artisan's guilds on the other side. The traders or merchant guild generally consisted of hereditary families proving certain brands of trade, who found into a corporation with “Jyestha or Jettaka⁵” (an elder man) at its head. During medieval period, a highly developed organization, the merchant guilds played an important part in the commercial life of the country and very much resembled the sabha on account of large part it played in the administration of local area⁶. The craft guilds formed as the sameness of occupation and a general community of interest. Residence in a local area and membership of a religious sect must have served as factors in the formation of merchant guilds rather than their members of one social caste or other. During medieval period under study, the merchant corporation in Telangana were mentioned in the contemporary inscriptions.

2. Method and materials

The paper is based on the primary sources like the inscriptions, Especially the Kannada inscriptions found in the present Telangana State. The data collected from the primary sources is corroborated with the secondary sources, and conclusion are derived at.

3. Discussion

Craft Guilds:

Buddhist texts mentioned several guilds of craftsmen and artisans who were both the producers and the sellers of their own goods and articles. The texts mentions the eighteen craft guilds which were organized under a head called Pramukha or Jettaka⁷.

The following characteristics may be noticed in the craft guild. Hereditary of profession, the son was apprenticed to the craft and art of his father. The manual skill, the talent for particular craft was an inheritance of the family from generation to generation.

- Localisation of industries with three important features
- Inside Cities
- Outside but in the proximity of the cities
- In the isolated parts of the country.

In ancient and medieval period, a person's profession was conditioned by his caste and caste of individual influenced in profession, so caste and heredity played an important role in craft guilds. According to Olden Burg, the Brahmin might as economic necessity often carried on other than the priestly profession. He might become a cultivator, a teacher or a thief, then he was perhaps treated with contempt but he remained a Brahmin⁸. According to Charles Bird woods, the trade guilds of great poly technique of cities of India are not always exactly co-incident with the sectarian or ethical caste of a particular class of artisans. Sometimes the same trade is pursued by means of different castes, and its guild generally includes every member of the trade. It represents without strict reference to any caste⁹ ⁷¹.

. The important craft guilds mentioned in the inscription were;

- The Teliki Varu (guild of oil millers)
- Paneanum Varu (different artisans)
- The Kampulu (guild of cultivators)
- The Salevaru or Tantuvayus (weavers)s

Telekivaru or Guild of Oil millers:

The Telekivaru is one of the more popular craft guilds during the period. This craft guild deals with the production and selling of oil besides the other socio-political activities. In the Nasik Inscription¹⁰ ⁷⁴ we find a reference to this oil – miller's guild. The Gupta Copper Plate Inscriptions of Skanda Gupta times from Indore¹¹ ⁷⁵ gives details about organization of

this craft guild. The head of this guild is referred to in the inscription of Mahattaka, Talika – Pattavila, Tailika Raja etc. and the oil men are generally styled of Taila Ghatakas, Tailaghatakas and Telligas¹².

The Satavahana inscriptions mentioned this craft guild as Tilaprishtakas. This craft guild is mentioned in many of the Kalyana Chalukya, Vengi Chalukya and Chola inscriptions. In some cases the guilds name suffixed with a number of a numerical figure thousand. It states that the community is known to have sub-divided itself into thousand families, ten of which are mentioned by name. The significance of thousand suffixes, Mallampalii Somashekar Sarma¹³ observes that this corporate body consisted of one thousand families. The number is enigmatic and its full significance as in the case of the number of other bodies is not known. It might represent either the number of families of the Telikas which originally immigrated to the South or the total membership of this corporate body consisting of elders, one from each of the thousand families. It appears to have become conventional to call guild, the Teliki one thousand. And that this tradition might have travelled from Andhradesa to the neighbouring Karnataka and Tamil regions of South.

Akhila Desala Teliki Varu is referred to in several inscriptions which had some relation with the territorial organisation of the guild. Desa as a territorial unit figured in many inscriptions of the medieval Andhradesha¹⁴. This is the expression may mean to a desa territorial units. An epigraph from Mukha – Lingam at Saka 1027 mentions this craft a Telika Kapulu. It is possible that Telika Kapulu were members in both the guilds that in the guild of Telika Kampulu by virtue of their being cultivators¹⁵.

Thus the craft guild of oil-merchants had controlled the trade, commerce and industry down to the end of medieval period. Their activities were not only confined to Andhradesha but also spread to Orissa, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu regions.

Panchanam varu:

Jatakas mention that guild is eighteen. These organized into guilds. Out of them only four are mentioned, referring to Carpenters, Smiths, Leather workers and Painters. The eighteen guilds that are referred to in the literary works both Buddhist and Jain and inscriptions of ancient India were, Potters, Silk worm, Gold Smith, Cooks, Perfumes, Barbers, Garland

makers, Vegetable Sellers, Betel sellers, Leather workers, Pressers (of oil, sugar cane etc.), Towel sellers, Printers, Braziers, Tailors, Milkmen, Hunters and Fishermen etc¹⁶.

The Panchalas are known as the Vira Panchala, Anjuvari Panchalas or simply Panchanam Varu, Panchala Varu. In inscriptions, it is mentioned by several names viz, of Panchanam Varu, Pachalas etc. It seems reasonably correct that all the expressions referred to above were synonymous and referred to the craft guild of Panchanam Varu. It is known from an epigraph found at Amaravti that Panchanam Varu belongs to Visva Karma Vamsa¹⁷.

A 12th century inscription gives a very interesting but a legendary origin of the Vira Panchala. It states that Visvakarma, son of Brahma was the progenitor of the architects and was the father-in-law of the Sun. Members of the Visva Karma Kula trace their ancestors to the five sons of Visva Karma of whom, Manu worked in iron, the second Maya in wood, third, Tvastaram in brass, copper and alloys and fourth Silpi in stone and the fifth Visvagna in a gold and silver and a jeweller¹⁸. An inscription, belonging to 7th century, from Palanadu¹⁹ taluq refers to certain Acharyas of the Kamma Kula in connection with the construction of a temple. Acharya of Kamma Kula, the members of the Visva Karma Kula add and still do as Achari, Acharya and Oza. Kamma Kula mentioned above does not mean the Kamma community as has been held in some quarters, but it means, a Kula which hailed from Kamma nadu a well known territorial division of great antiquity²⁰. The inscription of the period refers to certain interesting expressions regarding this guild viz. Panchanamvaru of the 74 Ahanas of world. “Padunalugu Tapala Panchanam varu”, Akkhiladesala Panchanam varu. The word Tapala found in the expression Padunalugu Tapalu Panchanam varu²¹ is not easy to explain. The figure 14 seems to imply a territorial connotation. Desa was a well known territorial division of medieval Andhradesha²².

The Panchalokhandi-Patulu found referred to in an inscription found at Srikakulam may mean the Masters of the five metals. They may be identical with the Panchanam Varu or Panchalohala Behara Mudedi varu²³.

Kampulu (Guild of Cultivators): The guild of cultivators was called the Kampulu. In the time honoured tradition of naming the guilds after the profession of the members of which, the guild was constituted. The literal meaning of word ‘Kampu’ means protectors or watchman but generally used mean Tillers of the Soil’. At present in Andhra Pradesh that the section of the fourth caste, whose traditional and hereditary profession had been cultivation of land are

referred to as Kampulu. These Kampulu of present day are generally found belong to the Reddi community. The members of the Kamma or Naidu community whose hereditary profession had also been agriculture are also included. Sometimes in the community of Kampulu but other sections of the fourth caste like the potters, the oil pressers, the weavers, the herdsmen etc. even if they inherited cultivation of land as their professions are hardly referred to as belonging to the community of Kampulu²⁴. The guild of cultivators is the Kampulu and their organisational or corporate activities are referred to in the inscriptions that are found in several parts of Andhradesha. The Katukuru and Matedu inscription refer to Nagaramu, along with Mahajanas, Kampus, Setti's as a corporate body in addition to the eighteen sects of Praja²⁵.

An inscription from Nellore, dated in AD 1257, throws light on the organisation of this guild. It registers a gift of land to the local temple by the cultivators of the Pedainadu, Perathinadu, Mungalarainadu, Kadaryasamaru, Kadaiyasinganadu, Pungainadi. This shows that the cultivators in each village are united in an ascending heirarchy of federation with the village unit at the bottom²⁶. The guild of agriculturists or cultivators was also referred to in the inscription of the Karnataka region. The Kukkanur inscription²⁷ of 1143 AD registers the gift by guild of agriculturists consisting of three hundred members. Some inscriptions found in Karnataka region refer to Okkalus²⁸. An epigraph belonging to Kakatiya of Ganapadideva gives the testimony to the prevailing custom that some people included in the list of eighteen castes lived on transportation business alone in the market towns. They were called the Perikavaru²⁹.

Sale Varu or Dharma Salis (Weavers):

The Sale Varu or Saliga community classified as the Padmasali and Pattusali was an important weaving community in the medieval South India in general and that of Andhradesha in particular. This was the same as Salega of Karnataka from the inscriptional evidences. It is clear that, Kamapatti, Mettewada, Bhimavaram, Achanta, Nagulapadu, Burgulapad, Mellacheruvu, Kokkirem, Tangevada, Dharmavaram, Kopparam, Alampur, Velpamadugu, Proddatur located in the present Karimnagar, Warangal, East Godavari, West Godavari, Nalgonda, Krishna Districts are famous for certain weaving community³⁰. In Cotton Muslin and Chintz were mainly woven. Muslin was called Sella. The Masulipatnam region was famous for its Muslin Chintz and was known as Vichitra³¹. The Nagnur inscription³² is

important as it is evident from this inscription that weavers of Sthala (territorial division). It is evident from this inscription that the Weavers may be a Federal Assembly and were authorised by it to make the gift.

The Lepakshi Copper Plate grant refers to Vastra bhedakas (dyers). Vastra rakshakas (sewers of clothes) and Devangas (spinners). People representing those crafts might have formed guilds of their own to look after their organisation and corporate activities³³. Building of temples and shrines in the consecration of the deities made of different materials and celebration of specific festivals in the temples by the weavers are reflection not only of their economic prosperity but also their ritual status. The relative importance of the guild of weavers and weaving community can be assumed from the policies of the state towards them. Not only state supported textile industry both internally and externally as evidenced from Motupalli charters also from the view of economic conditions. The Manosollasa³⁴ of the Chalukyan king, Someshwara refers to excellent textiles of Podalapura, Chirapalli, Naga Patna, and Cholapattana. An inscription discovered at Warangal refers to Pachai pattu (Yellow silk) and Dasuri Pattu (Silk manufactured at a place known as Dasura). The Motupalli inscription of the Kakatiya Ganapati Deva reduced the duties on all goods including silk in order to foster foreign trade in textiles³⁵. There are certain stray references to the weavers and their corporate activity in the inscription of our study. Naganur Inscription of A.D. 1228 refers to the Dharma Saliyas of Matiya Sthala, Matiya Sthalammu, Dharma Saleya Janulu. It records that Mali Setti and his son Venni Setti established on behalf of all the dharma sala of Mathya Sthala³⁶.

The Nagulapadu Inscription of AD 1225 registers a gift to the local temple by the people of eighteen Samayas of that place including the Salevaru or the weavers. Privileges and large scale concessions offered to them. It is also known through inscription from Guntur district that certain privileges are given viz. exempting the weavers from payment of tax for the first three years in a newly settled village³⁷.

Other Craft Guilds:

Other Craft guilds mentioned in the inscription are, such as; Kumbhalikas (potters) Gorakshakam, a Gollas boy as (cowherds), Rajakas (washer men), Kshaurkas (barbers), Basket makers, gunny bag makers and other steel vendors who sold their articles carrying them in baskets on their heads³⁸. It is likely that the persons following above these different crafts might have formed guilds for preservation and promotion of their corporate activities. From

the above, we may conclude in the period, there functioned organisations which were engaged both in trade and industry. It is also interesting to note that each of these organisations had several branches.

Conclusion:

Thus, the professional or the craft guild was open to all the people irrespective of their caste. Though a majority of them were conservative enough to be the followers of hereditary occupations, the partial hereditary character of profession was born out by a few pieces of contemporary evidence. Sulaiman states³⁹ that in the kingdom he visited people followed the profession of their respective castes. Barbosa⁴⁰ was also struck by the same features as may be seen from his remarks about the washer man of Malabar about whom he says that their sons must follow the same trade.

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